

ASSESSMENT OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION OF LIVESTOCK FARMERS IN EBONYI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed financial inclusion of livestock farmers in Ebonyi State using multistage sampling technique in the selection of 200 livestock farmers for the study. Data used for the study were primary data collected using questionnaire administered in the form of interview schedule. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as tables, frequency, mean and inferential statistics such as multinomial logit regression and principal component method of factor analysis. Results revealed that 58% of the respondents were males, with average age of 36 years and were married with mean household size of 5 persons. It was observed that the farmers spent an average of 16 years in school with 10 years of experience in livestock production that earned them average annual income of ₦1,411,300. The major livestock kept by the farmers included broilers (85%), sheep/goats (62%), layers (for eggs) (47%), pigs (32%) and cattle (16%). The type of livestock kept were influenced by demand for livestock (94%), prolific nature of type of livestock (88%), gestation period of livestock type (76%), availability of pasture (74%), price of livestock product (68%), climate of the area (68%), ease of management (58%), and marketing (56%). The financial inclusion index of 7 showed that financial inclusion measures dominant among the farmers were: own a bank account (96%), cash deposits (92%), access to ATM services (78%), access to mobile banking services (69%), access to ATM cards (66%), access to internet banking (66%), and POS services (64%). It was further observed that factors influencing financial inclusion of livestock farmers were from social, economic, institutional and managerial sources such as access to financial services (0.767), availability of market (0.622), marketing information (0.841), ease of internet banking services (0.792) and quality of financial services (0.620). From the Chi-square index of multinomial regression, it was observed that financial inclusion of livestock farmers has significantly influenced livestock production in the study area. The study concluded that financial inclusion of livestock farmers significantly influenced livestock production in the study area. The study recommended that financial institutions should deepen their measures of penetration in terms of access to insurance, credit and grant by making it more accessible to livestock farmers for effective financial inclusion

KEYWORDS: Assessment, Financial Inclusion, Livestock, Farmers, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

Livestock sector of agriculture plays vital role in socio-economic growth of the country. It also plays an important role in the rural economy as it improves the family income and generates a gainful employment in the rural sector, particularly among the landless labourers, small and marginal farmers. This sector provides large self-employment opportunities and is proven to be a boon for sustaining livelihood of the marginal farmers (Harisha, Subrahmanyeshwari, Veeranna, Sharma, Ravindrareddy and Punyakumari, 2021).

Livestock refers to domesticated animals such as cattle, goats, sheep, pig, rabbits and poultry birds of economic value to man which are good source of meat, milk, eggs, hide and skin (National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services [NAERLS], 2011). Adefalu, Usman, Omotesho, Aderinoye-Abdulwahab and Olateju (2013), posited that livestock contributes to the production of organic fertilizer and fuel and in the use of marginal nutritional resources which are not directly accessible to mankind and represents an important safety-net during the period of needs among rural folds. Otte and Chilonda (2002) in Oladimeji *et al.* (2017) reported that livestock is kept as a form of insurance and a means of storing savings. In addition, they further noted that the main functions of livestock production in pastoral households are to provide milk, and meat, to meet social obligations such as bride price, stock alliances and stock patronages and to insure against disaster: drought, epidemics and raids.

According to National Bureau of Statistics [NBS] (2016), Nigeria contributes more than 45% of the poultry in the West Africa sub-region and its livestock resources consists of 201,928,991 chicken, 16,722,190 cattle, 57, 937,176 goats, 36,372,233 sheep, and 7,770,599 pigs. By contrast, Nigeria has been adjudged as one of the world's fastest growing human populations, with a rate of increase of 2.6 percent per annum (FAO, 2016). Statistical surveys have shown that Nigeria is largely an animal protein deficient nation with annual total expenditure on food import of \$3 billion (Oladimeji, 2017).

The growth in livestock production in Nigeria faces significant challenges, including declining per capita production and poor livestock productivity (Oladimeji *et al.*, 2016; Otte and Chilonda, 2002). To address these challenges, increasing access to financial services is crucial. An inclusive financial system can provide livestock farmers with necessary savings, credit, payment, and risk management products (Fadun, 2014). This, in turn, can enhance their ability to invest in improved production systems, technology, and infrastructure, leading to increased productivity and output. By bridging the financial gap, inclusive financial systems can contribute to socioeconomic development and help meet the growing demand for nutritious and safe food (Habtamu, 2014; Sajuyigbe, 2017).

Financial inclusion refers to the provision of formal financial services such as basic savings bank account, credit facilities, and payment services, insurances and so on to the downtrodden and poor people at reasonably priced cost. According to Thomas (2018), financial inclusion includes the provision of affordable financial services such as access to payments and remittance facilities, savings, credits and insurance services by the formal financial system to those who tend to be excluded. World Bank (2014) noted that financial inclusion at the global level brings to light the fact that 2.5 billion people, i.e. about 40% of adult population remains without a bank account.

Financial Inclusion therefore is a deliberate strategic policy that facilitates access to, or makes available the use of all formal financial services to members of the public, groups or firms in an economy by financial service institutions. Financial inclusion is considered a powerful tool for inclusive economic growth as it is a means for empowering individuals, groups, and

businesses (Rasheed *et al.*, 2019). Financial inclusion for livestock enterprises is the nexus of economic diversification, growth and employment generation (International Monetary Fund, 2019).

The United Nations have flagged financial inclusion as a top main concern of the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals by 2030 (Molosag, 2016). With access to financial services, people would no longer need to rely on and transact exclusively in cash, or store cash savings at homes. Financial access connects people into the formal financial system, making day-to-day living easier and allowing them to build assets, mitigate shocks related to emergencies, illness or injury, and make productive investments (Thomas, 2018). Nevertheless, statistics reveals that, in Nigeria, 46.3 percent of adult population are not financially inclusive (Iwedi, 2020). This may not be unrelated to the lack of awareness and poor financial literacy particularly, among the rural populace which in effect, hinders socioeconomic wellbeing (Smyczek and Matysiewicz, 2014). It is on this background that livestock production calls for financial inclusion and entrepreneurial spirit to encourage social development and livestock entrepreneurship in the country.

Despite the significant contribution of livestock farmers to the socio-economic development of Nigeria, researches have suggested that financial exclusion is one of the biggest problem in developing or starting-up business (William and Ramana, 2019). However, available studies on financial inclusion concentrated on the financial inclusion of farmers in other agricultural subsectors in Nigeria and outside Nigeria. Some of these studies include: Umaru and Eshiozemhe (2022), who worked on financial inclusion and agricultural output nexus in Nigeria: An asymmetric approach; Kabuye, Nampijja and Musinguzi (2019) assessed financial inclusion and agricultural productivity among smallholder farmers in Uganda; and Ibenta, Akpunonu and Alajekwu (2021) who examined financial inclusion strategy and access to credit by micro small and medium scale enterprises (MSMEs) in Nigeria.

In view of this, much or little of such studies seems not to have been conducted on financial inclusion of livestock farmers in particular, hence it is imperative to fill the gap in the knowledge of financial inclusiveness of livestock farmers. In view of the importance, this study will pave way to stakeholders and policymakers in making appropriate policies that would ensure that rural farmers especially the livestock farmers are financially included. This study would also contribute to the understanding of whether financial inclusiveness enables livestock farmers' productivity. This could be done by providing adequate knowledge of sustainable financial inclusion of livestock farmers which facilitate several potential opportunities such as access to and use of financial services such as savings, credit, insurance and payments.

To address the seeming gap, this study described the socioeconomic characteristics of the livestock farmers and type of livestock kept; analyzed the financial inclusiveness of the livestock farmers; analyzed the factors influencing financial inclusion of livestock farmers in the study area; and determined the effect of financial inclusion on livestock production in the study area. The hypothesis of the study was that financial inclusion of livestock farmers has not significantly influence livestock production in the study area.

2. METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

The study was carried out in Ebonyi State Nigeria. Ebonyi State lies between latitude $07^{\circ}03^1N$ and longitude $05^{\circ}04^1E$ and $06^{\circ}45^1E$. Ebonyi has boundaries in the North with Benue State; South with Abia State; East with Cross River State, and West with Enugu State. According to National Population Commission (NPC) population projection of 2022,

projected Ebonyi State population at 3,313,289 people and landmass of approximately 5,932 square kilometers. Agriculture is the dominant source of livelihood of the people with majority of them residing in the rural areas. With its savannah and semi-tropical vegetation; humid climate, sandy and dotted marshy soils, the State is blessed with arable land for various agribusiness such as production of cash and food crops like yam, cassava, rice, palm produce; production of broiler, sales of feeds and feedstuff processing industries, etc. Coupled with agricultural activity is stone crushing popularly known as quarry and other small scale non-farm artisanal businesses like shoe mending, bakery, etc.

Sampling Technique

This study adopted multistage sampling procedure in selecting the number of respondents to be used for the study. The respondents were proportionately sampled at 25% proportionate from 1064, 931, and 665 list of livestock farmers in each of the zones (North, Central and South) using a list obtained from Ebonyi State Agricultural development programme (EBADEP). Hence, 266, 233 and 166 were selected from each zone. Again, purposive selection helped in selecting LGAs that are not contiguous to each other. Meanwhile, there was proportionate selection of 30% of the selected farmers from the zone. Hence, a total of 200 livestock farmers were selected with 80, 70 and 50 from Ebonyi North, Central and South zones. The detailed sampling procedure is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Sampling Procedure for selection of respondents for the study

Zones	25% from zone Proportionately	Farmers 30% Proportionate selection of livestock farmers
North (1064)	266	80
Central (931)	233	70
South (665)	166	50
Total		200

Source: Author’s computation

Data Collection

Data for this study were collected only from primary source. The data were collected using structured questionnaire.

Analytical technique

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to achieve the objectives of the study. Specifically, objectives (i) and (ii) were achieved using descriptive statistics such as percentage, table and mean. Objective (iv) was analyzed using multinomial regression analysis. Objective (iii) was analyzed using Principal Component Factor (PCF) analysis. The null hypothesis which states that financial inclusion of livestock farmers has not significantly influence livestock production in the study area was tested using Chi-square at 0.05 level of significance

Multinomial Regression Model

Multinomial regression analysis is a type of regression used to predict a nominal dependent variable with more than two response category. The implicit function of the model was;

$$Y = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_9) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, Y = dependent variables

X_1 to X_9 = independent variables

The model was explicitly defined as;

$$Y_i = a_0 + a_1X_1 + a_2X_2 + a_3X_3 + a_4X_4 + \dots + a_9X_9 + et \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where,

Y_i = Livestock production (types of livestock produced; 1 = broiler production, 2 = layers production, 3 = pig production, 4 = goats/sheep production, 5 = rabbit production, 6 = cattle production)

X_1 = Type of account (1 = savings, 2 = current, 3 business account, 4 = wallet account)

X_2 = Cash deposits (yes = 1; no = 0)

X_3 = access to the use of ATM machine (yes = 1; no = 0)

X_4 = Access to grants

X_5 = access to credit (₦)

X_6 = access to insurance services (yes = 1; no = 0)

X_7 = access to the use of Point of Sale (POS) (yes = 1; no = 0)

X_8 = access to ATM cards (yes = 1; no = 0)

X_9 = access to internet banking (yes = 1; no = 0)

$a_1 - a_9$ = Regression coefficients

et = error term.

Test of hypothesis

This hypothesis was tested using the p-value obtained from the estimation of the model. The P-value, which apart from the Pseudo R^2 also gave the overall significance of the model. The value obtained through estimation was 0.0000. In view of the fact that this value is less than the probability level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted that financial inclusion of livestock farmer has significant effects on livestock production in the study area.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of the Livestock Farmers and Type of Livestock Kept in the Study Area

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in the study as presented in Table 2. The socio-economic characteristics considered were; sex, age, marital status, educational attainment, household size, farm size, farming experience, annual income and membership association. Result revealed that about 58% of the respondents were males, while 42% were females. This implied livestock farming in Ebonyi State is male-dominated, potentially limiting women's economic empowerment. This gender distribution is consistent with other studies on livestock farming in developing countries. For instance, a study by Ogunnaike *et al.* (2019) found that 55.6% of livestock farmers were males, while 44.4% were females. Similarly, a study in Kenya reported that 61.1% of livestock farmers were males, while 38.9% were females (Mwangi *et al.*, 2020).

Result also revealed that 44% of the respondents were aged between 31 and 40 years, while 10% were aged 50 years and above. The average age of the respondents was 36 years. The dominance of active farmers in livestock farming is an indication that they will be favourably disposed for the exercise and be able to come out with good level of output. The result is in consonance with Ojo (2009) who showed that young people are dominating livestock farming in Nigeria. The presence of younger farmers (31 - 40 years) indicates a potential for succession and continuity. This result also implied that younger farmers are more receptive to new technologies and innovative practices; as this age group brings energy and innovative

ideas to the farming sector. This age distribution is similar to findings of Tadesse *et al.* (2019) who reported that about 43.1% of livestock farmers in Ethiopia were between 30 -39 years.

Result further revealed that majority (63%) of the respondents were married, while 33% were single. The dominance of married farmers in livestock farming may be connected to their use of the produce as food in meeting protein needs of the family and as well marketing some of them and using the proceeds to cater for their families. The result is in line with findings of Ovharhe, Achoja, Okwuokenye and Joe-James (2020) which revealed that livestock farming is mostly dominated by married farmers. The result also implied married farmers may involve family members in farming activities, increasing labour availability. Married farmers share decision-making responsibilities with spouses, that potentially improving farm management therefore suggest that married livestock farmers may have stronger social support networks, enhanced their well-being. This result is therefore consistent with Kabuye *et al.* (2019) who reported that 65.1% of livestock farmers in Uganda were married, while 30.5% were single.

The educational status of the respondents revealed that 52.5% of them were B.Sc/HND holders while 2.5% completed only primary schools and obtained FSLC. The average years spent schooling by the livestock farmers was 16 years. The high percentage of B.Sc/HND holders (52.5%) and an average of 16 years of schooling among livestock farmers indicates they are well-educated. From the result it could be deduced that quite a good fraction of the respondents were literates, can read and write and so can manipulate their livestock farming activities towards making good outcome. This result did not tow the path of Bautista Martínez (2023) which showed that the average schooling of the producers is secondary or junior high school. Similar studies found that 55.6% of livestock farmers in Nigeria held tertiary education and 51.2% in Uganda (Kabuye *et al.*, 2019; Tanimonure *et al.*, 2019).

Result further showed that majority (64%) of the respondents had household size of less than or equal to five (5) persons followed by 36% that had 6 – 10 persons. The average household size of the respondents was 5 persons. This implied that the family members can be used as a source of family labour, thereby reducing or holding back what could have been used to financially run the livestock farm. This result supports that of Oladele (2017) who indicated that household size is large and sufficient to argument farm labour cost. Similarly, Mkhize *et al.*(2020) and Tiamiyu *et al.*(2020) reported an average household sizes of 4.8 in South Africa and 5.2 in Nigeria respectively.

Enterprise experience has been identified as a driving force for start-up development. In this study, the average years of experience of the respondents was 10 years. Majority (44%) of the respondents had experience between 6 and 10 years while, 28% had 10 years and above. Meanwhile, 28% of the respondents also had ≤ 5 years of experience in livestock production. This finding is in consonance with Kabuye *et al.* (2019) who reported an average experience of 9.5 years.

The average annual income of the respondents was ₦1,411,300.0k with majority (40.5%) of the respondents earned between ₦500,001 and ₦1,000,000 annually while, few (11.5%) earned \leq ₦500,000. The average annual income of ₦1,411,300 suggests a decent income level among livestock farmers. This income level implies potential for investment in livestock farm expansion. The result also implies that the benefits derived from livestock production are numerous and this may be responsible for their interest in farming or rearing livestock. Similar studies found average incomes of ₦1,201,100 in Nigeria (Tiamiyu *et al.*, 2020) and ₦1,051,200 in Uganda (Kabuye *et al.*, 2019).

Majority of the livestock farmers belonged to association as justified by 70% while, 30% of the livestock farmers did not belong to association. The high percentage (70%) of livestock farmers belonging to associations facilitates knowledge sharing, access to resources, and collective bargaining power. Similar studies found association membership rates of 65.2% in Nigeria (Ogunnaike *et al.*, 2019) and 60.5% in Uganda (Kabuye *et al.*, 2019). Association membership improves productivity and income among livestock farmers (Tiamiyu *et al.*, 2020).

Table 2: Distribution of Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Livestock Farmers in the Study Area

Socioeconomic Variables	Category	Frequency (N = 200)	Percentage (%)	Mean (\bar{X})
Gender	Male	116	58	
	Female	84	42	
Age (Years)	≤ 30	64	32	36
	31-40	88	44	
	41-50	28	14	
	Above 50	20	10	
Marital Status	Single	66	33	
	Married	126	63	
	Widowed	8	4	
Educational Level	FSLC completed	5	2.5	16
	JSS completed	29	14.5	
	SSCE completed	33	16.5	
	OND completed	16	8.0	
	BSC/HND	105	52.5	
Household size	M.Sc/Ph.D	12	6.0	
	≤ 5	128	64	5
Experience (years)	6-10	72	36	
	≤ 5	56	28	10
	6-10	88	44	
Above 10	56	28		
Annual income (₦)	≤ 500,000	21	11.5	1,411,300
	500,001 – 1,000,000	81	40.5	
	1,000,001 – 1,500,000	26	13.0	
	1,500,001 – 2,000,000	36	18.0	
	Above 2,000,000	34	17.0	
Membership of Association	Yes	140	70	
	No	60	30	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Type of Livestock Kept by the Livestock Farmers in the Study Area

Type of livestock kept by the farmers has direct effect on their financial inclusiveness. Result as presented in Table 3 revealed that broiler production (85%), sheep/goats production (62%), layers production (47%), pig production (32%), cattle production (16%) and rabbit production (3%) were the major livestock stock kept in the area. Keeping different types of livestock is a common practice among livestock farmers, as it encourages diversification. Critical analysis shows that poultry, goat/sheep, and piggery are the major livestock production engaged in and kept by the livestock farmers. This diversity is possible due to factors such as: climate, culture, market demand and available resources. This finding is in

line with the work of Singh, Kumar and Kumar (2020) who explored aspects of livestock farming, focusing on diversity in animal keeping.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents according to Type of Livestock production

Types of Livestock Production	Category	Frequency* (N = 200)	Percentage (%)
	Broiler	170	85
	Layers	94	47
	Pig	64	32
	Rabbit	6	3
	Sheep/goats	124	62
	Cattle	32	16

Source: Field Survey, 2024; * = Multiple Response

Factors Influencing Choice of Livestock Kept by the Livestock Farmers

Livestock farming is crucial for food security and economic development in Nigeria. However, farmers' choice of livestock kept were influenced by several factors as presented in Table 4. Result revealed that livestock farmers consider multiple factors when selecting which livestock to keep. Market demand emerged as the most significant factor influencing farmers' choices, with 94% of the respondents citing it as a key consideration. This finding is supported Kamal *et al.* (2019) reported that market demand drives livestock diversity in which 85% of farmers prioritize market requirements. Similarly, Adebayo *et al.* (2018) found that market demand influences 90% of farmers' decisions, further validating the importance of market demand in livestock production. Farmers prioritize livestock with high reproductive performance, with 88% of the respondents consider prolific nature while, 76% focused on gestation period. This finding is consistent with Olukosi, Buvanendran, and Gyawu (2016) who reported that 80% of livestock farmers prioritize prolific nature. However, Mehedi (2017) found that only 60% of farmers consider gestation period, suggesting regional variations in productivity priorities. A significant proportion of livestock farmers (74%) prioritized pasture availability. This is not in line with the findings of Nolan (2024), who reported 55% of livestock farmers in Australia considered pasture availability a key factor. Similarly, 68% of the respondents were influenced product prices when making choice of livestock to keep. This finding disagrees with Tadesse *et al.* (2015), who reported that 75% of farmers in Ethiopia prioritized product prices. Cost of feeds (50%) is another factor influenced the choice of livestock kept among the farmers. This is not in line with Tekle (2019) who reported that 70% in South African. These findings highlight regional differences in livestock production decisions.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents according to Factors Influencing Choice of Livestock Kept

Factors	Frequency* (N = 200)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Demand for livestock	188	94	1 st
Prolific nature of type of livestock	176	88	2 nd
Gestation period of livestock type	152	76	3 rd
Availability of pasture	148	74	4 th
Price of livestock product	136	68	5 th
Climate of the area	136	68	5 th
Ease of management practices	116	58	7 th
Ease of marketing	112	56	8 th
Cost of feed	100	50	9 th

Source: Field Survey, 2024; * = Multiple response

Financial Inclusiveness of the Livestock Farmers

Financial inclusiveness among livestock farmers has significant implications for policy initiatives, financial institutions, and agricultural extension programs. Financial inclusiveness which indicates having access to financial services and products for effective transactions and marketing of livestock products has been analysed using livestock farmers as proxy. From the analysis, financial measures for financial inclusiveness having a bank account (96%), access to cash deposits (92%), access to the use of ATM machine (78%), access to mobile banking services (69%), access to ATM cards (66%), access to internet banking (66%), access to the use of POS services (64%), access to credit (54%), access to insurance services (54%) and access grants (32%). The financial inclusion index was approximately 7. This means that the overall financial inclusion index of approximately 7 suggests moderate financial inclusion, underscoring the importance of continued efforts to improve financial access and usage among livestock farmers. This is in line with the study of Kumar *et al.*, (2019) who inferred that enhancing financial inclusiveness among livestock farmers can have far-reaching implications for economic growth, poverty reduction, and sustainable agricultural development. By addressing the financial needs of farmers, stakeholders can contribute to a more resilient and productive agricultural sector. This finding is consistent with Demirguc-Kunt *et al.* (2018) finding who reported 69% of adults in developing economies have a bank account. This high rate of account ownership suggests that farmers are increasingly integrated into the formal financial system. However, variations exist in access to advanced financial services, with 66% accessing ATM cards and internet banking, and only 32% accessing grants. These findings imply that policymakers should focus on enhancing financial inclusion by expanding access to digital financial services, particularly mobile banking, which 69% of farmers utilize (Aker and Mbiti, 2010). Furthermore, the relatively low access to credit (54%) and insurance services (54%) highlights the need for targeted financial support mechanisms. Grant funding can play a crucial role in supporting agricultural development and poverty reduction.

Table 5: Percentage Distribution of Livestock Farmers according to Financial Inclusiveness

Financial measures	Frequency * (N = 200)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Ownership of bank account	192	96	1 st
Access to cash deposits	184	92	2 nd
Access to the use of ATM machine	156	78	3 rd
Access to mobile banking services	138	69	4 th
Access to ATM cards	132	66	5 th
Access to internet banking	128	64	6 th
Access to the use of POS services	124	62	7 th
Access to credit	108	54	8 th
Access to insurance services	108	54	8 th
Access grants	64	32	10 th
Financial Inclusion Index (FII)		6.67	

Source: Field Survey, 2024; * = Multiple response; FII = 7

Factors Influencing Financial Inclusion of Livestock Farmers in the Study Area

Factors that induced financial inclusion of livestock farmers have been assessed using PCF analysis with three major components as the driving factors. The naming of these factors in three was based on Kaiser's (1958) rule of thumb that variables with 0.4 as applied by Nwibo and Okorie (2013). These component factors include social, economic, institutional and managerial factors as presented in Table 6. Social factors play a pivotal role in shaping financial inclusion, particularly in rural areas where livestock farming is prevalent. Access to financial services (0.767) is a critical social factor, as it enables farmers to manage their financial transactions efficiently. This finding is supported by Kumar *et al.* (2019) who found that financial inclusion increased farmers' income by 25%. Improved farmers' access to credit (0.735) also significantly contributes to financial inclusion, thereby allowing farmers to invest in their livestock businesses. This implied access to credit enables farmers to purchase quality livestock, feed, and equipment, leading to improved productivity and income. This is in line with IFAD (2019) report that 70% of smallholder livestock farmers used credit to invest in their farms.

Furthermore, legal identity (0.641) and Know Your Customer (KYC) services (0.553) facilitate farmers' access to formal financial services, reducing the risk of financial exclusion. This finding is in line with the work of Demirguc-Kunt *et al.*, (2018) who reported identification is a critical component of financial inclusion, as it provides a unique identifier that allows individuals to access financial services and conduct transactions securely.

Economic factors also significantly influence financial inclusion among livestock farmers. Improved farmers' access to insurance (0.745) mitigates financial risks associated with livestock farming, enabling farmers to invest in their businesses with greater confidence. This corroborated with report of IFAD (2019) that insurance play a critical role in reducing the vulnerability of smallholder farmers to risk, enabling them to invest in their farms and improve their productivity. Availability of market (0.622) and marketing information (0.841) also contribute to financial inclusion by enabling farmers to make informed decisions about their livestock products (World Bank, 2020). However, the cost of banking services (0.447) remains a significant barrier to financial inclusion, highlighting the need for affordable financial services (Sarma and Pais, 2011). Institutional factors, particularly the ease of internet banking services (0.792), also significantly influence financial inclusion among livestock farmers highlighting the importance of digital financial services in expanding financial access to rural areas.

Finally, managerial factors, such as quality of financial services (0.620) and attractiveness of bank products (0.665), also play a crucial role in promoting financial inclusion among livestock farmers. Banks must offer tailored financial products that meet the specific needs of livestock farmers, ensuring that financial services are accessible and user-friendly. This is supported by Aker and Mbiti (2010) who reported that mobile phones and digital financial services can increase access to financial services for the unbanked. The authors further noted that, mobile phones have the potential to increase access to financial services for the unbanked and underbanked, particularly in rural areas where traditional banking infrastructure is lacking.

Table 6: Varimax Rotated Component Matrix on Factors Influencing Financial Inclusion of Livestock Farmers in the Study Area

Factors	Social	Economic	Institutional	Managerial
Access to financial services	0.767	0.116	0.168	-0.080
Improved farmers access to credit	0.735	0.083	0.233	0.265
Quality of financial services	-0.327	0.184	0.382	0.620
Improved farmers access to insurance	-0.297	0.745	0.382	0.050
Availability of market	-0.343	0.622	-0.381	-0.143
Marketing information	0.053	0.841	0.273	0.003
Attractiveness of bank products	0.200	0.133	-0.101	0.665
Legal identity	0.641	0.244	0.317	0.010
Cost of banking services	0.128	0.447	-0.313	-0.303
Proximity to financial institutions	-0.183	0.172	-0.001	0.283
Ease of withdrawal and deposits	0.346	-0.149	-0.107	0.087
Ease of internet banking services	0.047	-0.115	0.792	0.007
Know your customer (KYC) services	0.553	-0.041	-0.072	-0.305

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Effects of Financial Inclusion on Livestock Production in the Study Area

Multinomial regression was used to determine the effects of financial inclusion of livestock farmers on livestock production in the study area. Livestock production in this study was classified into six (6) categories which include; broiler production, layers production, pig production, goat/sheep production, rabbit production and cattle production. It is important to note that multinomial regression is a choice model with categories of dependent variables, which is desirable to choose a reference category to compare with. In this case, broiler production was chosen as the default base category because, it has the highest frequency score among the categories. The comparison among the categories was drawn with respect to the base category – *broiler production*. The regression result gave rise to five (5) models, namely; layers production, pig production, goat/sheep production, rabbit production and cattle production, relative to broiler production.

The result revealed a significant relationship between financial inclusion and livestock production in the study area. The likelihood ratio test ($\chi^2 = 167.986$, $p < 0.0001$) confirmed the model's goodness of fit, indicating a strong association between the dependent and independent variables. The pseudo R^2 value of 0.594 further supported the model's explanatory power. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have shown a positive impact of financial inclusion on agricultural productivity (Oke, 2019; Adeyemi, 2018).

Specifically, the following financial inclusion indicators were statistically significant: owning a bank account, cash deposits, access to ATM machines, access to grants and access to POS services. The negative coefficient of access to credits on layers production can be as a result

of high interest rates on credits leading to increase financial burdens on farmers, reducing layers production investments. Credit repayment pressures may also lead farmers to divert resources from layers production to other activities. This finding is in line with Ogunnaike *et al.* (2019), who found that financial inclusion increased poultry production among smallholder farmers in Nigeria. However, access to credits exhibited a negative and statistically significant relationship, contrasting with Tiamiyu *et al.* (2020), who found that access to credit increased livestock production among farmers in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Financial inclusion indicators had a positive effect on pig production; financial inclusion indicators such as owning a bank account, access to ATM machines, access to POS services, and access to ATM cards demonstrated positive and statistically significant coefficients at the 10% level. This implies that owning a bank account, access to ATM machines, access to POS services, and access to ATM cards significantly influenced pig production in the study area. This finding aligns with Mkhize *et al.* (2020), who found that financial inclusion increased livestock productivity among smallholder farmers in South Africa.

Similarly, financial inclusion indicators such as owning a bank account, cash deposits, access to ATM machines, access to grants, access to credits, access to insurance services, access to POS services, access to ATM cards, and access to internet banking exhibited positive coefficients. Access to grants and access to credits were significant at different levels of probability, indicating their substantial impact on goat/sheep production. This finding supports Kabuye *et al.* (2019), who found that financial inclusion improved livestock productivity among smallholder farmers in Uganda.

In rabbit production relative to broiler production, financial inclusion indicators such as owning a bank account, cash deposits, access to grants, access to insurance services, and access to internet banking demonstrated positive and statistically significant coefficients. This finding is consistent with Oladele (2017), who found that financial inclusion increased agricultural productivity among smallholder farmers in Nigeria.

Finally, in cattle production relative to broiler production model, financial inclusion indicators such as owning a bank account, cash deposits, access to insurance services, access to POS services, and access to ATM cards bore positive and statistically significant coefficients. This implied financial inclusion enhances farmers' ability to invest in quality livestock and inputs as it increases farmers' access to market information, improving cattle production decisions. This finding aligns with Adeyeye (2018), who found that financial inclusion improved agricultural productivity among smallholder farmers in Nigeria.

In summary, the multinomial regression analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between financial inclusion and livestock production, particularly in layers, pig, rabbit, goat/sheep, and cattle production. The findings justify the importance of financial inclusion in enhancing livestock productivity and this is consistent with previous studies (Kabuye *et al.*, 2019; Mkhize *et al.*, 2020). Financial inclusion improves farmers' access to credit (Oke, 2019), reduces transaction costs (Adeyemi, 2018), and enhances financial management (Ogunnaike *et al.*, 2019).

The null hypothesis was tested using the p-value obtained from the estimation of the model. The P-value, which apart from the Pseudo R² also gave the overall significance of the model. The value obtained through estimation was 0.0000. In view of the fact that this value is less than the probability level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted that financial inclusion of livestock farmer has significant effects on livestock production in the study area.

Table 7: Multinomial Regression Result of Effects of Financial Inclusion on Livestock Production in the Study Area

Factors	Livestock production									
	Layers production		Pig production		Rabbit production		Goat/sheep production		Cattle production	
	Coefficients (β)/SE	Wald	Coefficients (β)/SE	Wald	Coefficients (β)/SE	Wald	Coefficients (β)/SE	Wald	Coefficients (β)/SE	Wald
Ownership of bank account	0.25 (0.051)	24.029***	1.956 (1.097)	3.178*	45.453 (96.088)	0.224ns	16.295 (8.312)	3.843**	0.862 (0.342)	6.353**
Access to cash deposits	0.717 (0.257)	7.783***	1.294 (0.992)	1.699ns	15.314 (16.863)	0.825ns	18.252 (7.544)	5.854**	13.53 (3.706)	13.329***
Access to the use of ATM machine	17.855 (6.62)	7.275***	1.056 (0.570)	3.436*	41.984 (91.892)	0.209ns	0.265 (0.865)	0.094ns	1.096 (1.348)	0.661ns
Access to grants	0.101 (0.049)	4.249**	1.006 (0.632)	2.530ns	13.846 (6.023)	5.285**	1.119 (0.586)	3.646*	0.475 (0.815)	0.340ns
Access to credit	-0.278 (0.096)	8.386***	-0.168 (0.469)	0.128ns	12.647 (7.197)	3.088*	0.438 (0.674)	0.422ns	0.423 (0.968)	0.191ns
Access to insurance services	0.627 (0.536)	1.368ns	0.137 (0.484)	0.081ns	14.343 (8.922)	2.584ns	2.181 (0.699)	9.735***	17.613 (8.226)	4.584**
Access to the use of POS services	0.968 (0.523)	3.426*	1.009 (0.543)	3.453*	26.333 (28.366)	0.862ns	1.127 (0.715)	2.484ns	2.067 (1.082)	3.649*
Access to ATM cards	0.811 (0.572)	2.010ns	1.080 (0.558)	3.738*	2.527 (543.93)	0.000ns	0.353 (0.833)	0.180ns	15.173 (6.095)	6.197**
Access to internet banking	0.114 (0.525)	0.047ns	0.963 (0.600)	2.578ns	12.073 (515.645)	0.001ns	2.546 (0.797)	10.205***	1.617 (1.015)	2.538ns
Intercept	32.317 (9.707)	11.084***	0.247 (1.473)	0.028ns	6.313 (3.194)	3.907**	36.205 (4.544)	63.483***	46.895 (14.896)	9.911***
-2 Log likelihood ratio	322.230									
Chi Square (X^2)	167.986									
Pseudo R ²	0.594									
P-value	0.0000									

Source: Field Survey, 2024; the figures in parenthesis are standard errors; ns = not significant; ***, ** and * = significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level of probability, respectively.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study on assessment of financial inclusion of livestock farmers in Ebonyi State, it was concluded that access to financial services, improved farmers access to credit, quality of financial services, improved farmers access to insurance, availability of market, marketing information, attractiveness of bank products, legal identity, cost of banking services, ease of internet banking services, know your customer (KYC) services were factors influencing financial inclusion of livestock farmers in Ebonyi State. Therefore, based on the findings, it recommended that:

- Financial institutions should deepen their measures of penetration in terms of access to insurance, credit and grant by making it more accessible to livestock farmers for effective financial inclusion.
- Targeted financial inclusion initiatives: financial institutions should design and implement targeted financial inclusion initiatives focusing on livestock farmers, particularly women to enhance their access to financial services. This could include: simplified banking procedures, mobile banking services, access to microcredits and financial literacy training.
- Livestock production training and support: provide training and support to livestock farmers, emphasizing: best practices in broiler, sheep/goats, layers, pig, and cattle production, marketing strategies, disease management and feed formulation and nutrition. This will enhance productivity and profitability.
- Market development and access: improve market access and development for livestock products: establish livestock markets, enhance market information dissemination, promote value addition (e.g., processing, packaging) and facilitate linkages between farmers and buyers.

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